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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study		Quantification of esterified oxylipins following HILIC-fractionation of lipid classes	
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Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	Solid-Phase Extraction	pH adjustment	Disodium hydrogen phosphate
Solid-Phase Extraction	Mixed Mode	Were internal standards used?	Yes
Deposition method	-	Internal standards used	d4-9-HODE, d4-13-HODE, d8-5-HETE, d8-12-HETE, d8-15-HETE

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Acetic acid	Number of separation dimensions	One dimension
Separation type 1	LC	Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP
Detector	Mass spectrometer	MS type	QQQ
MS vendor	SCIEX	Ion source	ESI
MS Level	MS ²	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	Low resolution	Resolution at MS ²	Low
Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Profile mode	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Solvent blank, Internal standard blank
Quality control	Yes	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Guidelines followed	EMA		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	No	Are metadata available?	No
Raw data upload	No		

Sample Descriptions

QC 1 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C
Instant sample preparation	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Additives	None	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No

NIST SRM 1950 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C
Instant sample preparation	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Additives	None		

Supplementation Study / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C
Instant sample preparation	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Additives	None		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) Oxylipins[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Oxylipins	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Full structure	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
alpha cleavage			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	manually
Data manipulation	Smoothing	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

1) Oxylipins[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
d4-9-HODE	172.3	9-HODE	
d4-9-HODE	172.3	13-HODE	
d4-13-HODE	198.1	15-HODE	
d4-13-HODE	198.1	9-HOTrE	
d4-13-HODE	198.1	13-HOTrE	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	8-HETrE	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	12-HETrE	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	15-HETrE	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	5-HETE	
d8-12-HETE	184.2	8-HETE	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	9-HETE	
d8-12-HETE	184.2	11-HETE	
d8-12-HETE	184.2	12-HETE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	15-HETE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	5-HEPE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	8-HEPE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	9-HEPE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	11-HEPE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	12-HEPE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	15-HEPE	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	18-HEPE	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	4-HDHA	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	7-HDHA	
d8-5-HETE	116.1	8-HDHA	
d8-12-HETE	184.2	10-HDHA	
d8-5-HETE	184.2	11-HDHA	
d8-12-HETE	184.2	13-HDHA	
d8-12-HETE	184.2	14-HDHA	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	16-HDHA	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	17-HDHA	
d8-15-HETE	226.0	20-HDHA	

Type of quantification	Calibration line	Type of calibration line	Solvent based
Species calibration line	9-HODE, 13-HODE, 9-HOTrE, 13-HOTrE, 8-HETrE, 12-HETrE, 15-HETrE, 5-HETE, 8-HETE, 9-HETE, 11-HETE, 12-HETE, 15-HETE, 5-HEPE, 8-HEPE, 9-HEPE, 11-HEPE, 12-HEPE, 15-HEPE, 18-HEPE, 4-HDHA, 7-HDHA, 8-HDHA, 10-HDHA, 11-HDHA, 13-HDHA, 14-HDHA, 16-HDHA, 17-HDHA, 20-HDHA	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	S/N >5 and 80% < accuracy < 120%
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Multiquant
Batch correction	No		

2) FA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Full structure	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	manually
Data manipulation	Smoothing	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No

2) FA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
d4-C18:2 n6		C18:2 n6	
d4-C20:5 n3		C18:3 n3	
d8-C20:4 n6		C20:4 n6	
d5-C20:5 n3		C20:5 n3	
d5-C22:6 n3		C22:6 n3	

Type of quantification	Calibration line	Type of calibration line	Solvent based
Species calibration line	C18:2 n6, C18:3 n3, C20:4 n6, C20:5 n3, C22:6 n3	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	S/N >5 and 80% < accuracy < 120%
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Multiquant
Batch correction	No		

